

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

A Hybrid CNN–LSTM Approach for Predicting Software Vulnerability Exploitability

Santosh Saklani^{1*}, Anshul Kalia¹, Sumesh Sood¹

¹ Department of Computer Science, Himachal Pradesh University, India

 OPEN ACCESS

Received: 03/02/2026

Accepted: 23/03/2026

Published: 09/04/2026

Citation: Saklani S, Kalia A, Sood S (2026) A Hybrid CNN–LSTM Approach for Predicting Software Vulnerability Exploitability. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 19(12): 820-829. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v19i12.151>

* **Corresponding author.**

saklani.mailto@gmail.com

Funding: None

Competing Interests: None

Copyright: © 2026 Saklani et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment (iSee)

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

Abstract

Objectives: Software vulnerabilities pose a serious threat to cybersecurity. When vulnerabilities are publicly disclosed, organizations must quickly determine which vulnerability requires immediate attention. This study focuses on predicting software vulnerability exploitability at disclosure time using textual information, enabling timely prioritization to reduce the risk of exploitation.

Methods: A hybrid model combining Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) is used to predict disclosure-time exploitability of a vulnerability. The model uses textual vulnerability information available at disclosure, which includes CVE descriptions and associated CWE names. Vulnerability records are obtained from the National Vulnerability Database (NVD), and exploitability labels are derived from ExploitDB based on the availability of public exploits. Performance is evaluated using accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. **Findings:** The proposed CNN–LSTM model effectively predicts software vulnerability exploitability using textual data. The model achieved an accuracy of 92.33% and an F1-score of 92.08% when using a combined textual input consisting of CVE descriptions and CWE names. Comparative and ablation studies show that the CNN–LSTM architecture outperforms standalone CNN and CNN–BiLSTM models in overall effectiveness. **Novelty:** The study investigates how CWE information contributes to predicting software vulnerability exploitability. It explores the use of a hybrid CNN–LSTM model to classify the exploitability of vulnerabilities using textual data. The model is also evaluated on recently disclosed vulnerabilities to assess its generalization to new, unseen data and its usefulness for early prioritization.

Keywords: Exploitability prediction; software vulnerability; deep learning; convolutional neural network; Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE)

1 Introduction

Software vulnerability management is essential for the security and reliability of modern information systems. Software vulnerabilities are frequently exploited by attackers, which leads to persistent security breaches. The volume of disclosed vulnerabilities continues to grow with the increase in software development. It further expands the potential attack surface. In 2024, public databases recorded more than 40,000 newly

disclosed security vulnerabilities⁽¹⁾. However, only a small fraction is actively exploited, which creates challenges for security teams in deciding which vulnerabilities to address first. Vulnerability prioritization helps organizations to determine which weaknesses are most likely to be exploited. By ranking vulnerabilities according to risk, security teams can allocate resources more effectively, apply patches where they matter most, and minimize overall cybersecurity exposure.

When a vulnerability is disclosed publicly, a Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures identifier (CVE-ID)⁽²⁾ is assigned to it. The National Vulnerability Database (NVD) stores CVE-IDs along with additional information such as severity ratings, affected products, and CWE classifications⁽³⁾. At the time of public vulnerability disclosure, information that directly indicates exploitability, such as the availability of Proof-of-Concept (PoC)⁽⁴⁾ or public exploits, is unavailable. This lack of timely information restricts accurate risk assessment during the period between vulnerability disclosure and patch release, when vulnerabilities are most likely to be exploited.

Security analysts rely on the Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS) to assess newly disclosed vulnerabilities. CVSS provides standardized severity metrics, but the manual nature of CVSS scoring and its dependence on expert judgment limit its usefulness for real-time prioritization. In addition to this, CVSS does not clearly show how likely a vulnerability is to be exploited. Therefore, organizations require automated, data-driven approaches that can estimate the exploitability of vulnerabilities at the early stage, using the information available at vulnerability disclosure.

Machine Learning (ML) techniques have gained attention in recent years for their application in vulnerability assessment. ML methods use historical vulnerability data to predict the likelihood of exploitation. Liu et al.⁽⁵⁾ developed a TextRCNN-based classifier for cross-site scripting (XSS) vulnerabilities. The model achieved good accuracy, but its focus on a single vulnerability category limits its applicability to other vulnerability categories. Le et al.⁽⁶⁾ applied novelty detection techniques on social media data for cyber threat identification. The presence of noise and misinformation makes it less relevant for threat classification.

Fang et al.⁽⁷⁾ proposed fastEmbed, which uses textual embeddings with CVSS scores to predict exploit availability. CVSS scores are not assigned at the time of disclosure; therefore, this approach is less suitable for early-stage vulnerability assessment. Jacobs et al.⁽⁸⁾ trained a model using enterprise telemetry data. Their model showed good results, but the use of proprietary data limits its scope and reproducibility. Yin et al.⁽⁹⁾ proposed a BERT-based model for exploitability prediction. The model shows high performance, but high computational cost can make its deployment difficult in environments with limited resources.

de Sousa et al.⁽¹⁰⁾ and Huang & Wu⁽¹¹⁾ used social media data with public vulnerability datasets. But the noisy nature of social media and limited technical details remained challenges. Bhatt et al.⁽¹²⁾, in their research found that factors like vulnerability type, severity and system configuration play an important role for the prediction of security threats. But many of these features become available only after disclosure. Similarly, Okutan & Mirakhorli⁽¹³⁾ used CNN to assess severity and exploitability, introducing the product hygiene index derived from product-specific attributes. Although effective in certain contexts, their model's reliance on narrowly scoped features reduces applicability across diverse vulnerability types. Suciu et al.⁽¹⁴⁾ introduced the expected exploitability metric, which uses proof-of-concept exploits and technical write-ups. However, it depends on data that is unavailable at the disclosure of vulnerability.

The main limitations of prior studies are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Limitations of prior studies in exploitability prediction

Study/Studies	Limitation
⁽⁶⁾ , ⁽¹⁰⁾	Overreliance on social media signals (e.g., Twitter) and dark-web signals introduce noise, misinformation, and lacks structured vulnerability features, which limits reliability and robustness.
⁽⁵⁾ , ⁽¹³⁾	Narrowly scoped models (e.g., focusing solely on XSS, product-specific data, or software structure) ignore broader contextual information, which limits their ability to generalize across different vulnerabilities.
⁽⁸⁾ , ⁽¹²⁾	Reliance on proprietary datasets or enterprise telemetry limits applicability and generalizability.
⁽⁹⁾	Models like BERT are computationally expensive, which limits scalability and feasibility on low-resource hardware.
⁽⁷⁾ , ⁽¹⁴⁾	Models that rely on post-disclosure indicators (e.g., PoC or CVSS scores) are less useful because these signals are not available at an early stage.

To address these limitations, a hybrid CNN–LSTM model is proposed to predict the exploitability of software vulnerabilities using textual information available at vulnerability disclosure. The key motivation of this study is to develop a system that can be used as a tool to assist the vulnerability management process. By predicting exploitability early, the proposed model enables security teams or software vendors to fix vulnerabilities with the highest likelihood of exploitation. The contributions of this study are as follows:

- A hybrid CNN–LSTM model is trained for predicting exploitability of software vulnerability using textual data available at the time of vulnerability disclosure.

- We compare the performance of the proposed CNN-LSTM model with alternative deep learning architectures, including standalone CNN and CNN-BiLSTM models, to evaluate the effect of architectural design on predictive performance.
- A case study is conducted on the latest disclosed vulnerabilities to validate the performance of the proposed CNN-LSTM model. The results demonstrate the model's ability to predict the exploitability of modern vulnerabilities.

2 Methodology

This section describes the development of the hybrid CNN-LSTM model for predicting software vulnerability exploitability. It includes the problem formulation, dataset preparation, model architecture, and evaluation methodology.

2.1 Problem Formulation

The vulnerability exploitability prediction is framed as a binary text classification problem. Given a vulnerability description and its associated CWE category, the goal is to learn a function:

$$F : X \rightarrow Y$$

where X represents the merged textual input (CVE description and CWE name) and $Y \in \{0, 1\}$ denotes the exploitability label. A label of 1 indicates that a publicly available PoC exploit exists for the vulnerability, while 0 indicates no such exploit exists.

2.2 Dataset Construction and Labelling

The dataset is prepared by integrating vulnerability records from the National Vulnerability Database (NVD) and exploit information from Exploit-DB⁽¹⁵⁾. For each CVE entry, the CVE identifier, textual description, and associated CWE name are extracted from NVD. Exploit-DB is used to determine whether a corresponding publicly available PoC exploit exists for each CVE. The CVE-ID serves as the common key for mapping records between the two databases, as illustrated in Figure 1.

After cleaning (removal of duplicates and incomplete entries), 23,850 vulnerabilities appearing in both databases are identified and labelled as exploitable. To balance the dataset, an equal number of vulnerabilities (23,850) not appearing in Exploit-DB are randomly selected from NVD and labelled as non-exploitable. The final dataset consists of 47,700 samples.

Each vulnerability is assigned a binary label based on CVE-ID presence in Exploit-DB. A vulnerability is labelled as exploitable (1) when its CVE-ID is found in Exploit-DB and non-exploitable (0) otherwise. The absence of a CVE-ID from Exploit-DB does not imply that the vulnerability is inherently non-exploitable, but rather that no public exploit had been reported at the time of data collection.

Some NVD entries lack CWE assignments or contain placeholder values such as "Unknown." These cases are addressed using keyword-based pattern matching applied to CVE descriptions. Additionally, CVEDetails⁽¹⁶⁾ is queried to recover missing CWE information. Through this process, each vulnerability record is assigned a valid CWE label, which ensures that both unstructured (CVE description) and structured (CWE name) textual features are available for all samples used in model training and evaluation.

2.3 Input Representation and Preprocessing

For training the proposed model, the textual description of each CVE is combined with its corresponding CWE name to form a single input sequence. This merged representation allows the model to learn semantic patterns from unstructured descriptions and categorical weakness information.

The textual input is pre-processed to make it compatible with deep learning models. All the text is converted into lowercase and tokenized using TensorFlow's tokenizer. Before tokenization, basic text cleaning is applied to the vulnerability descriptions. This step removes special characters, URLs, and extra spaces that do not contribute useful information. Common stop words are also removed to reduce noise in the text and improve the overall quality of the data representation.

To control the size of the input space, the vocabulary is restricted to the 20,000 most frequently occurring tokens. In addition, each token sequence is either padded or truncated to a fixed length of 300 tokens so that all inputs have the same size, which helps the model process the data efficiently during training.

The tokenized input can be expressed as:

$$X = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_L)$$

Fig 1. Dataset creation and labelling process for exploitability prediction.

where $L = 300$ denotes the fixed maximum sequence length and w_i represents the i -th token in the sequence. Each token is mapped to a dense vector through an embedding layer, producing an embedding matrix $E \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times d}$, where $d = 240$ denotes the embedding dimension.

2.4 Hybrid CNN-LSTM Model Architecture

2.4.1. Model Motivation

In this study a hybrid deep learning architecture combining Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) with Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks is used to predict the exploitability of software vulnerabilities using textual descriptions. CNN layers capture local textual patterns such as keywords and short phrases that signal exploit-related conditions, while LSTM layers model long-range dependencies and preserve contextual information of the textual data. This enables the model to learn both localized and sequential characteristics of vulnerability text.

To the best of our knowledge, hybrid CNN-LSTM architectures have not previously been applied to exploitability prediction using CVE descriptions and CWE classifications. Although CNN-LSTM components have been explored in related work on software vulnerability detection based on source-code metrics⁽¹⁷⁾, their use for early-stage exploitability prediction using disclosure-time textual information remains largely unexplored.

2.4.2. Convolutional Feature Extraction

After tokenizing and padding the input text, each sequence is converted into dense vector representations through an embedding layer with 240 dimensions. The embedding vectors are initialized randomly and updated during training to capture meaningful semantic features. These embeddings are then fed into a one-dimensional convolutional layer with 240 filters and a kernel size of 5. ReLU activation is applied to extract informative local patterns from the input. This operation enables the model to capture short word patterns that are strongly associated with exploitability. The convolution operation is defined as:

$$c_i = f(W_c \cdot E_{i:i+k-1} + b_c)$$

where $f(\cdot)$ denotes the ReLU activation function and b_c is a bias term. Max-pooling with pool size 2 is applied to reduce dimensionality.

2.4.3. Sequential Modelling with LSTM

The pooled feature representations produced by the convolutional layer are then provided to the LSTM layer, which consists of 240 units. It learns dependencies in long sequences and preserves the order and context of the textual data. The LSTM hidden state at time step t is defined as:

$$h_i = \text{LSTM}(c_t, h_{t-1})$$

where c_t denotes the input feature at time step t and h_{t-1} is the hidden state from the previous step. To reduce overfitting, a dropout layer with a rate of 0.5 is applied after the LSTM.

2.4.4. Classification and Optimization

The output of the LSTM is forwarded to a fully connected dense layer with 240 neurons, and ReLU activation is applied to introduce non-linearity. The final output layer consists of a single neuron with a sigmoid activation function. It produces a probability score that reflects the likelihood of a vulnerability being exploitable:

$$\hat{y} = \sigma(W_o h_T + b_o)$$

The model is trained using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001 and binary cross-entropy as the loss function:

$$\mathcal{L} = -[y \log(\hat{y}) + (1 - y) \log(1 - \hat{y})]$$

The model is trained with a batch size of 32. Early stopping is employed with validation loss monitoring to prevent overfitting and restore the best-performing weights.

The overall CNN–LSTM architecture and training flow are shown in Figure 2.

2.5 Training and Evaluation

To examine the reliability of the proposed model, preliminary experiments were first carried out using five-fold cross-validation. The results obtained from different folds were largely similar, suggesting that the model performs consistently. After observing this stability, the final experiments are conducted using a hold-out evaluation method. In this approach, the dataset is divided into 80% for training and 20% for testing. In addition, 10% of the training data is used as a validation set to assist with parameter tuning and early stopping during training. Throughout the training process, the accuracy and loss of both the training and validation sets are observed to monitor the learning behavior of the model and to minimize the chances of overfitting. This setup provides a practical way to evaluate the model while supporting stable learning and better generalization to unseen data.

Fig 2. CNN–LSTM architecture for predicting vulnerability exploitability.

2.6 Model Variants for Comparison

To assess the impact of different model architectures, two alternative deep learning variants, a standalone CNN and a CNN–BiLSTM, are implemented alongside the proposed CNN–LSTM model. The same dataset and preprocessing pipeline are used to train all three models. This comparison focuses on lightweight architectures suitable for resource-constrained deployment, ensuring a fair and controlled evaluation.

2.7 Case Study on 2025 Vulnerabilities

A case study is performed using vulnerabilities disclosed in 2025 to assess the practical performance of the proposed CNN–LSTM model. The dataset includes 130 vulnerabilities, equally divided between exploitable and non-exploitable cases based on Exploit-DB presence.

Although the sample size is small, it reflects the limited number of vulnerabilities with verified exploits available in early 2025. This limitation arises because only a small subset of newly disclosed vulnerabilities receives confirmed exploit information. The purpose of this case study is not broad statistical generalization but to assess how the model performs on completely unseen and contemporary vulnerabilities, which is essential for practical cybersecurity deployment. This dataset is separate from the training and earlier test datasets. Therefore, it ensures an unbiased assessment of the model on fresh data. We applied the same preprocessing steps as applied during training of the model to keep things consistent.

3 Results and Discussion

This section presents the performance of the CNN–LSTM model and compares it with alternative architectures and prior studies. It also discusses the results in detail.

3.1 Vulnerability Exploitability Prediction

Table 2 presents the performance of the proposed CNN–LSTM model using merged textual input consisting of the CVE description and the corresponding CWE name. The model achieved an accuracy of 92.33%, a precision of 92.84%, a recall of 91.32%, and an F1-score of 92.08%. These results indicate a high and balanced predictive capability across all evaluation metrics.

Table 2. CNN-LSTM performance for exploitability prediction

Classifier	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
CNN-LSTM	0.9233	0.9284	0.9132	0.9208

Figure 3 shows the confusion matrix. The model correctly identified 4488 true negatives and 4286 true positives. It produced 395 false positives and 371 false negatives. The high number of correct predictions and relatively low false-positive rate show the model’s effectiveness to distinguish exploitable from non-exploitable vulnerabilities. High precision is important in vulnerability prioritization, as false alarms can lead to inefficient allocation of security resources.

Fig 3. Confusion matrix of the CNN-LSTM model predicting exploitability of software vulnerabilities.

3.2 Comparison of Model Variants

To analyse the impact of different architectures, the CNN–LSTM model is compared with a standalone CNN and a CNN–BiLSTM architecture. The results are visually presented in Figure 4. The CNN–LSTM model achieved the highest overall accuracy, precision, and F1-score. The CNN–BiLSTM obtained a slightly higher recall (0.9238), which shows a stronger ability to capture exploitable cases, but it has lower precision and accuracy. The standalone CNN performed competitively, but it remained less effective than hybrid models.

Fig 4. Comparative performance of CNN, CNN–BiLSTM, and CNN–LSTM architectures across accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score

3.3 Impact of CWE Feature on Different Architectures (Ablation Study)

An ablation study is conducted to measure the impact of incorporating CWE information into the input representation. All models are trained using two input settings: (1) CVE description only and (2) combined CVE description and CWE name. The results are presented in Table 3.

Performance improved across all evaluated architectures when CWE information is included. The CNN–LSTM model showed the largest improvement, with accuracy increasing from 0.8394 to 0.9233, along with substantial gains in precision and F1-score. Similar trends are observed for the CNN and CNN–BiLSTM models.

These results demonstrate that CWE names provide structured, high-level semantic cues that complement unstructured CVE descriptions.

Table 3. Ablation study: Effect of CWE inclusion on different architectures

Model	Input Feature(s)	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
CNN	CVE Description	0.8397	0.8287	0.8467	0.8397
CNN	CVE Description + CWE Name	0.9148	0.9105	0.9154	0.9129
CNN- BiLSTM	CVE Description	0.8396	0.8188	0.8624	0.8400
CNN- BiLSTM	CVE Description + CWE Name	0.9092	0.8938	0.9238	0.9086
CNN-LSTM	CVE Description	0.8394	0.8562	0.8065	0.8306
CNN-LSTM	CVE Description + CWE Name	0.9233	0.9284	0.9132	0.9208

3.4 Comparison with Related Studies

Table 4 compares the proposed CNN–LSTM model with existing studies related to vulnerability exploitability prediction. The model achieved balanced performance across all evaluation metrics compared to prior methods.

The decision tree classifier reported an accuracy of 88.53% and an F1-score of 0.877. The BCE classifier based on binary unigrams achieved a precision of 0.83, but complete evaluation metrics are not provided. While the fine-tuned BERT model achieves strong results, it requires significantly higher computational resources.

Le et al. (6) and Fang et al. (7) reported uneven precision–recall trade-offs, which negatively affected their overall F1-scores. In contrast, the proposed CNN–LSTM model maintains a better balance between precision and recall, leading to more stable overall performance.

Table 4. Comparison with related studies.

Study	Feature Extraction Method	Classifiers	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
(12)	Handcrafted features	Decision Tree	.8853	0.9470	0.8100	0.8770
(14)	Binary unigrams	BCE classifier	-	0.83	-	-
(9)	Fine-tuned BERT	LSTM	0.9112	0.9116	0.9182	0.9051
(7)	fastText	fastEmbed	0.9330	0.6210	0.2510	0.3560
(6)	TF-IDF	novelty classifier	-	0.8510	0.5170	0.6430
Proposed Model	Word Embedding	CNN–LSTM	0.9233	0.9284	0.9132	0.9208

3.5 Case Study Analysis

To evaluate generalizability to recent, unseen vulnerabilities, the trained CNN–LSTM is tested on a dataset of 130 vulnerabilities disclosed in 2025. The results, summarized in Table 5 show an accuracy of 0.8846, a precision of 0.8676, a recall of 0.9076, and an F1-score of 0.8872.

Performance on the smaller and newer dataset is slightly lower than on the larger training-test set, but the model maintains high recall. This is important in operational cybersecurity settings, where minimizing missed exploitable vulnerabilities is a critical requirement.

Table 5. Performance of CNN-LSTM on the new dataset

Classifiers	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
CNN-LSTM	0.8846	0.8676	0.9076	0.8872

3.6 Practical Implications for Vulnerability Management

The proposed exploitability prediction model can support practical vulnerability management activities. It helps security analysts and software vendors identify vulnerabilities that have a higher likelihood of exploitation. These predictions allow

organizations to prioritize critical vulnerabilities, allocate resources more efficiently, and plan patching strategies in a more effective manner. Early identification of high-risk vulnerabilities after disclosure allows security teams to address the most serious threats at an earlier stage. This approach improves vulnerability management and strengthens proactive cybersecurity efforts.

4 Conclusion

This work explored the use of a hybrid CNN–LSTM model to predict the exploitability of software vulnerabilities using textual descriptions together with CWE information. The result showed that adding CWE features is helpful, as it allowed the model to separate exploitable vulnerabilities from non-exploitable ones. The model showed high performance across all the performance metrics, which indicates that it can learn meaningful patterns from both the textual descriptions and the structured vulnerability data.

In comparison with other models, such as a CNN and CNN–BiLSTM, the CNN–LSTM consistently produced better results. This shows that combining convolutional layers for feature extraction with LSTM layers for sequence learning is well suited for this type of prediction task.

The model is also tested on a 2025 case study dataset, and it performed well with an accuracy of 0.8846. These results indicate that the model can reliably handle recent vulnerability data. This shows its potential use in practical security applications, such as vulnerability triage and exploitability assessment.

The model performs well, but it has some limitations. Its accuracy depends heavily on the quality of textual descriptions and CWE labels, so missing or unclear information can reduce performance. Future work may focus on adding more contextual information, such as exploit repositories, threat intelligence data, and time-based patterns. Additionally, the CNN–LSTM model could be evaluated against transformer-based models and tested on larger, more varied datasets to assess performance and efficiency.

In summary, the proposed CNN–LSTM model offers an effective and efficient approach for predicting vulnerability exploitability by making use of both CVE descriptions and CWE classifications.

5 Acknowledgements

The authors declare that no external funding, or institutional assistance was received for the conduct of this study.

6 Author's Contribution

Conceptualization of study problem: SS (Ph.D.Student), Experimental design: SS, DAK, and DSS, Software or algorithm: SS, Data generation: SS, Data analysis: SS and DAK, Research guidance: DAK and DSS Original drafting: SS, Editing & reviewing: DAK (Assistant Professor) and DSS (Chairperson).

References

- 1) National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), National Vulnerability Database: statistics results. Gaithersburg (MD). NIST. 2024. Available from: <https://nvd.nist.gov/vuln/search>.
- 2) The MITRE Corporation, CVE: frequently asked questions (FAQs). Bedford (MA). MITRE. 2023. Available from: <https://www.cve.org/ResourcesSupport/FAQs>.
- 3) National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), National Vulnerability Database (NVD): general FAQs. Gaithersburg (MD). NIST. 2024. Available from: <https://nvd.nist.gov/general/FAQ-Sections/General-FAQs>.
- 4) Donnell WS. Proof-of-concept exploit. New York (NY). Ziff Davis. 2024. Available from: <https://www.pcmag.com/encyclopedia/term/proof-of-concept-exploit>.
- 5) Liu K, Zhou Y, Wang Q, Chen X. Vulnerability severity prediction with deep neural network. *Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Big Data and Information Analytics*. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1109/BigDIA.2019.8802851>.
- 6) Le BD, Wang G, Nasim M, Babar MA. Gathering cyber threat intelligence from Twitter using novelty classification. *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Cyberworlds*. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CW.2019.00058>.
- 7) Fang Y, Liu Y, Huang C, Liu L, Wang Y. FastEmbed: predicting vulnerability exploitation possibility based on ensemble machine learning algorithm. *PLoS One*. 2020;15(2):e0228439. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0228439>.
- 8) Jacobs J, Romanosky S, Adjerid I, Baker W. Improving vulnerability remediation through better exploit prediction. *Journal of Cybersecurity*. 2020;6(1):tyaa015. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cybsec/tyaa015>.
- 9) Yin J, Tang M, Cao J, Liu S, Zhang J. Apply transfer learning to cybersecurity: predicting exploitability of vulnerabilities by description. *Knowledge-Based Systems*. 2020;210:106529. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knosys.2020.106529>.
- 10) Sousa D, Faria E, Miani R. Evaluating the performance of Twitter-based exploit detectors. *Proceedings of the XX Simpósio Brasileiro de Segurança da Informação e de Sistemas Computacionais*. 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5753/sbseg.2020.19257>.

- 11) Huang SY, Wu Y. Dynamic software vulnerabilities threat prediction through social media contextual analysis. *Proceedings of the 15th ACM Asia Conference on Computer and Communications Security*. 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3320269.3405435>.
- 12) Bhatt N, Anand A, Yadavalli VSS. Exploitability prediction of software vulnerabilities. *Quality and Reliability Engineering International*. 2021;37(2):648–663. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qre.2754>.
- 13) Okutan A, Mirakhorli M. Predicting the severity and exploitability of vulnerability reports using convolutional neural networks. *Proceedings of the International Workshop on Engineering and Cybersecurity of Critical Systems*. 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3524489.3527298>.
- 14) Suciu O, Nelson C, Lyu Z, Dumitraş T. Expected exploitability: predicting the development of functional vulnerability exploits. *Proceedings of the 31st USENIX Security Symposium*. 2022.
- 15) Offensive Security, Exploit Database. New York (NY). Offensive Security. 2024. Available from: <https://www.exploit-db.com>.
- 16) CVE Details, CVE Details. 2024. Available from: <https://www.cvedetails.com>.
- 17) Agbenyegah FK, Asante M, Chen J, Akpaku E. Predicting software vulnerability based on software metrics: a deep learning approach. *Iran Journal of Computer Science*. 2024;7(4):801–812. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42044-024-00195-8>.